

**Stabilizing an ultrathin MoS₂ layer during electrocatalytic hydrogen evolution
with a crystalline SnO₂ underlayer**

Supporting Information

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Figure S1. Cross-section scanning electron micrographs of AAO membranes anodized for *a)* 3 h, *b)* 4 h, *c)* 6 h or *d)* 8 h in 1 wt-% phosphoric acid at 195 V.

Figure S2. Thickness characterization of 40 c atomic layer deposited MoS₂ films. *a)* Spectroscopic ellipsometry: measured and fitted curves in dots and solid line, respectively; the fit yields an MoS₂ thickness of 9 nm. *b)* Step edge measurement by AFM, yielding a thickness of 10 nm.

Figure S3. X-ray diffraction pattern of AAO / SnO₂ / MoS₂ composite electrodes. Comparison of samples with an as-deposited SnO₂ film (orange) and an annealed SnO₂^T film (red). All electrodes feature 10 nm SnO₂, 40 c of MoS₂ and pore lengths of 18.5 μm. Diffraction peaks corresponding to Al (from frame; COD 2300250) and Ni (from backside-contact; COD 2102278) were observed for both samples. The annealed sample features diffraction peaks corresponding to crystalline cassiterite (COD 1000062). No crystalline MoS₂ was observed.

Figure S4. Electrocatalytic performance of AAO / c-SnO₂ / MoS₂ composite electrodes for different pore lengths: 8.6 μm (black), 10.0 μm (red), 14.3 μm (blue) and 18.5 μm (green). a) Cyclic voltammograms, measured from +0.2 V to -0.7 V (vs. SHE), scan rate 50 mV/s, step size 2 mV. b) Average steady-state current densities vs. pore length for various applied potentials (vs. SHE). The electrodes feature a 20 nm thick c-SnO₂ layer and 40 c of MoS₂. Electrode area 0.0314 cm², performed in 0.1 M H₂SO₄ electrolyte.

Figure S5. Linear sweep voltammogram for an AAO / c-SnO₂ / a-MoS₂ composite electrode featuring pore lengths of 8.6 μm, a 20 nm c-SnO₂ film and 40 c of MoS₂, recorded from +0.22 V to -0.68 V (vs. RHE). Scan rate 50 mV/s, step size 2 mV, electrode area 0.0314 cm². Performed in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ electrolyte.

Table S1. EIS fit parameters. All measurements performed in 0.1 M H₂SO₄ electrolyte.

MoS ₂ thickness / ALD cycles	R_u / Ω	R_{ct} / Ω	α_{ts}	$Y_{ts} / 10^{-6} \text{Ss}^\alpha$
10	82.5	12900	0.949	103
25	104	1210	0.921	303
40	79.8	107	0.896	824
75	98.7	109	0.789	1130

Table S2. Comparison of the HER activities of different amorphous MoS₂ based electrocatalysts.

Electrodes	Loading (mg/cm ²)	Current density (mA/cm ²)	Overpot. (mV)	Electrolyte (H ₂ SO ₄)	preparation (catalysts)	Ref. in main text
MoS _x /PDOPA@MWCNTs ^a	0.283	10	214	0.5 M	Wet chemical	[11]
MoS ₃	0.2	10	160	1 M	Electrodeposition	[41]
MoS ₆ AD ^b	0.1	10	161 ^c	0.5 M	Electrodeposition	[42]
MoS _x QD ^d	----	5	800	0.5 M	Wet chemical	[40]
MoS ₂ /graphene foam	----	10	264	0.5 M	Atomic layer deposition	[43]
MoS _x /N-doped CNT ^e	----	10	110	0.5 M	Wet chemical	[46]
MoS ₂ /TNTAs ^f	1.2	10	189	0.5 M	Atomic layer deposition	[9]
a-MoS _x /PbTe QD ^d /TNA ^f	4.5	10	138 ^c	0.5 M	Electrochemical anodization	[44]
MoS _x	0.05	10	210	0.5 M	Wet chemical	[45]
MoS ₂ /SnO ₂ /AAO ^g	0.16 ^h	10	220	0.5 M	Atomic layer deposition	This work

^a polydihydroxyphenylalanine (PDOPA), multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs), ^b anodic deposition, ^c resistance-corrected, ^d quantum dots, ^e carbon nanotubes, ^f titanium oxide nanotubes arrays, ^g anodic aluminum oxide, ^h The catalyst loading was calculated assuming a perfect hexagonal structure with an edge length of 310 nm, a pore diameter after SnO₂ ALD of 340 nm and pore lengths of 7.5 μm (averaged values, determined by SEM).